

SOME INTERACTIVE METHODS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING (FLT) THAT ARE IN USE TODAY

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Annotation: The main purpose of this article is to provide an assessment of the role played by methods in education process, though there is also an account of the main different methods of foreign language teaching (FLT) that are in use today. To start with, it is noticeable to mention that knowledge of different approaches gives foreign language teachers a proper background reference to their own stand on pedagogical matters and classroom practice, furthermore helps them to understand the importance of FLT in this century.

Key words: teacher, learner, methods, linguistic, knowledge, foreign language, different approaches, technique, communicative approach, beneficial, self-activity

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi metodlarning ta'lim jarayonidagi rolini baholashdan iborat, garchi u bugungi kunda qo'llaniladigan chet tilini o'qitishning asosiy turli usullarini tavsiflaydi. Boshlash uchun shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, turli xil yondashuvlarni bilish chet tili o'qituvchilariga pedagogik masalalar va sinf amaliyoti bo'yicha o'z pozitsiyalari haqida to'g'ri tasavvur beradi, shuningdek, ularga ushbu asrdagi ahamiyatini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qituvchi, talaba, metodlar, tilshunoslik, bilim, chet tili, turli yondashuvlar, metodika, kommunikativ yondashuv, foydalilik, mustaqil-yondashuv

Аннотация: Основная цель данной статьи - дать оценку роли методов в образовательном процессе, хотя здесь также приводится описание основных различных методов обучения иностранному языку, которые используются сегодня. Для начала следует отметить, что знание различных подходов дает преподавателям иностранных языков правильное представление об их собственной позиции по педагогическим вопросам и практике в классе, а также помогает им понять важность в этом столетии.

Ключевые слова: учитель, ученик, методы, лингвистика, знание, иностранный язык, разные подходы, методика, коммуникативный подход, полезность, самодеятельность.

The growing interest in many parts of the world in Modern Methods of Teaching English brings with it the question of how it should be done – how curriculum, subject, matter, and methodology should differ from the familiar norms developed in the past. A lot has been written on traditional teaching English, and until recently, the demand for the information on modern methods of teaching English has been limited.

For a teacher, methods prescribe what materials and activities should be used, how they should be used and what the role of the teacher and how it should be like in the classroom. For learners, methods define what approach to learning the learner should take and what roles the learner should adopt in the classroom. All methods include prescriptions for the teacher and the learners. All methods are a pre-packaged set of specifications of how the teacher should teach and how the learner should learn derived from a particular theory of language and a theory of language learning.

An approach is the most abstract of all three concepts that refers to the linguistic, sociolinguistic principles underlying methods and techniques. For getting more information about what is approach it is beneficial to reckon about the following concerns, like what an approach is influenced by including the inquiry of what the theory of language is followed by how the language is viewed. Additionally, concerning the question of how the learners learn the language, it is simply significant to bear in mind what the psychological and cognitive processes are involved such as habit formation, induction, inference or generalization. In all cases, what conditions need to be met for these learning processes should be activated. A technique is, on the other hand, the narrower of all these two; in fact, it is a just single produce to use in a kind of place. To illustrate, I would like to prove my sentences by the following graph:

Different approaches in foreign language teaching practice there are different approaches and they differ in different countries as well as the types of approaches are used differently. First of all, we have to analyze the types of approaches which are used by foreign teachers in other countries. As we looked at theoretical part, an approach is a theory of language teaching. According to William, the theory of language underlying these methods is structural

linguistics, and though there are some differences between British and American structuralism, both movements saw language as “a system of structurally related elements for the encoding of meaning, the elements being phonemes, 114 morphemes, words, structures, and sentence types”.

For instance, the main features are the importance part of oral aspects of the language, running out from the accordant of the written language. It is fact that, these conceptions appeared to offer a scientific basis for FLT, which are considered to have transformed teaching from an art into a science.

As for Arthur these were summarized in the following five ideas: 1. Language is a speech. 2. A language is what its native speakers say; it is not what someone thinks they ought to say. 3. Languages are different from each other's. 4. A language is a huge number of habits. 5. Teach the language, not about the language. All choices are based on their theory of learning behavioristic habit – forming conceptions. All above-mentioned terms are currently in an active implementation both in foreign and local language teaching institutions in Uzbekistan, in the scope of communicative approach as it is an umbrella term to describe the methodology which teaches students how to communicate efficiently. It also emphasis on students responsibility for their own learning. It includes cooperating within group, self-activity and dictionary work. The first step of communicative approach is language acquisition rather than conscious learning. As for Krashen “acquisition is a natural process, similar to the way children develop ability in their first language a it is subconscious process when students are not aware of the fact they are acquiring language but are using the language for communication”.

After concluding this, it is understandable for us that Grammar is no more based on the collection of rules, as it is consisting of structures as well. Moreover, studying a language means to collect and analyzing all these steps of the language and rules to combine word with each other.

Nowadays many books and articles are written to attract attention to this point. In planning curricular and methods, it has been suggested that an understanding of students and their needs, interest, abilities, likes, dislikes, and developmental status should take precedence over other considerations. By using modern pedagogical and technological methods, and by the way introducing leading styles of teaching, teach growing generations, the system of speaking easily in these languages can be developed fully.

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